

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Creative and critical thinking (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing a good paper (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 12-14)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-42)

THE IMPORTANCE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this paper, I will discuss the importance of academic writing. Writing has become an important task for centuries. Depending on the topics, there are diverse ways and distinctive writing styles. For instance, Historians have a way of writing, and Novelists or Theologians have their way of writing. Writing is particularly fundamental in the academic realm, and the level of success of an academic author is intimately linked to his writing skills. Therefore, acquiring skillful writing skills requires effort and dedicated time. This is one of the reasons Euclid University provides its Ph.D. students with a specific module on the fundamentals of writing at the very beginning of the program. This paper analyses the importance of academic writing by reviewing the content of the "**ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)**" by Euclid University.

First, I will examine the resource "**ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)**" by Euclid University. This course pack aims to provide fundamental guidance on academic paper writing. It covers topics such as essay writing, rules of punctuation, differences between American and British English, plagiarism, style guide, CMS Crib Sheet, Latin abbreviations and expressions, and finally, sample correction to

papers. I will also examine the BASIC ACA-401 TUTORIAL VIDEO and the Sample RP Review video.

2) FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

Writing is an important part of academic work and requires mastery of some key steps. Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7). Thus, drafting a good essay requires careful planning and execution, starting with three foundational steps. First, an early start-up involves dedicating time to reading, research, thinking, and writing. Second, clearly defining the question and analyzing the task helps to understand and address the topic effectively. Lastly, draft an initial plan to outline your ideas, guide research, and organize your approach.

Beyond the foundational steps, writing a good essay requires seven key steps, including (i) defining and analyzing key terms by organizing ideas into a structured plan that identifies the key question, the information required, and the sequence for presenting points, (ii) researching credible sources, and taking structured notes from your initial readings, (iii) organizing your ideas by writing an essay plan to structure the essay, (iv) writing the essay beginning by producing a first which includes a clear introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction transitions from general to specific, presenting the thesis and a roadmap for the essay. The body comprises well-structured paragraphs that build the argument with evidence and analysis, while the conclusion restates the thesis, summarizes key points without introducing new information, (v) referencing the essay to avoid plagiarism is crucial for ensuring clarity, coherence, and compliance with academic standards, (vi) editing the essay ensuring it is clearly and logically structured, and (vii) handing the essay.

The BASIC ACA-401 TUTORIAL provides specific guidance on paper format. This video particularly shows how to use the response paper template and format documents using Microsoft Word. On the other hand, the Instructor's Sample Review Video shows how to use the Microsoft Word review tab to address comments, especially the Track Changes Review function in Microsoft Word to accept or reject tracking done.

While reading the sections on “starting the essay, including the pyramid of basic steps in writing an essay” as well as the section on “researching the topic,” I noticed that the transition between the first two objectives is unclear. There seems to be an overlap between the general overview of essay writing basics and the steps for writing a good essay. Additionally, the first and second layers of the pyramid (figure 1: Basic steps on writing an essay), starting from the base, appear to be integrated into the first step, seem to be embedded in the first step, even though they are presented as separate stages in the pyramid.

3) CREATIVE AND CRITICAL THINKING

Writing a good essay also requires considering both creative and critical thinking. Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9). It serves as the foundation for generating and expanding ideas by using brainstorming, mind mapping, and exploring diverse perspectives to uncover fresh concepts and innovative approaches to the topic.

Critical thinking encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas (op. cit.). It serves as the foundation to evaluate the relevance, importance, and validity of the concepts analyzed or generated during the creative phase by asking questions to go deeper into the importance of concepts and arguments. (for example, asking why an example is important to your argument)

In the academic field, we often must deal with both types of thinking. At some point, we may use more critical thinking than creative thinking and vice versa, but the two types of thinking are interlinked. By combining creative thinking to explore possibilities and critical thinking to evaluate possibilities and structure the essay, we give ourselves the possibility to redefine varying viewpoints, discuss their strengths and weaknesses, and use relevant evidence to support our argument.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A GOOD PAPER

Essay writing also requires attention to specific stylistic rules. I have listed eight rules of thumb provided in the ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1 (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 13-14). The thesis should be presented early and remain the central focus throughout the essay. Avoid vague generalities and instead use concise language and robust evidence to support arguments. Maintain clarity by employing short sentences, active voice, and logical transitions between ideas. Thoughtful engagement with alternative perspectives strengthens the argument, while thorough editing ensures the essay is polished and error-free. Adhering to the rules of thumb in academic writing is essential for producing clear, professional, and well-structured, high-quality essays. Those rules also help strengthen argumentation and ensure a logical flow throughout the essay.

5) AVOID PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a serious academic offense. Writing good academic papers requires to know what plagiarism is and how to avoid it. “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). Therefore, the only way to avoid plagiarism is to properly cite an author when using his work. Giving credit to an author’s work means citing ideas provided by the author and indicating the source used. To do so, we can use In-text

citations, using quotations and paraphrases, or long quotations. Of course, not everything needs to be cited, especially information that is considered common knowledge. However, it is not enough to avoid plagiarism by simply quoting or paraphrasing an author's idea. We must also provide a properly formatted list of works cited to give appropriate credit to those sources.

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is essential for ensuring consistency in writing, especially when multiple authors contribute to a publication. A style guide is considered “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2024, 41). While creative writers may not rely on style guides, they can benefit from them to maintain consistency and reduce proofreading time. Style guides cover various elements of writing, such as punctuation, grammar, and formatting, and are crucial for technical and business writers to meet customer expectations. Freelance writers should develop style guides for each client to improve customer satisfaction and maintain consistency across projects.

While reading the section on style guides, I have learned that Euclid recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and that a style guide helps maintain consistency, reduces time spent on proofreading and revisions, and improves customer satisfaction. It also provides valuable insights into what to consider when analyzing an author's style guide. I also understand that such work requires an important level of organization, and success will not be achievable without it.

7) CONCLUSION

This course is a crucial step to go further in acquiring relevant academic writing skills. As has been mentioned in this paper, writing a good academic paper requires a combination of careful planning, structured execution, and attention to detail. The foundational steps of early preparation, task analysis, and outlining guide the process, while the seven key steps ensure that the essay is logically structured, well-researched, and properly referenced. Critical and creative thinking play vital roles in developing and evaluating ideas, allowing for a balanced approach to writing. Additionally, adherence to stylistic rules and avoiding plagiarism are essential for producing clear, professional, and credible work. A style guide further supports consistency, improves efficiency, and ensures the quality of academic writing, making it an indispensable tool for writers at all levels. With all that in mind, I am ready to embark on this journey, which will involve writing scholarly papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2016. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

Gulma, Kabiru, dir. 2022. *Instructor's Sample Review Video*. YouTube.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.